

Influence of Unemployment on the Nigerian Child

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of unemployment on the Nigerian child sustainable development in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. Three objectives guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of parents in three selected wards from the Local Government (Samaru, Basawa and Dogarawa), numbering 400. A total of 80 parents constituted the study sample. Data was collected using validated structured questionnaire tagged Nigerian Child Sustainable Development Questionnaire (NCSDQ), developed by the researchers based on the study objectives. The instrument has a reliability index of 0.85. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency and percentages. The study found that 26.3% of the respondents are fully employed and satisfied with their jobs, 58.7% of the respondents were just working, but not satisfied with their jobs, 32.6% of the respondents agreed to be self-employed while 91.6% of the respondents were unemployed. The study further found that negligence of agricultural sector and other natural resources due to over dependence on crude oil is the major cause of unemployment with 90%, insecurity with 81.2% and low standard of education with 85%. The findings on the influence of unemployment on the child found that 76.3% of the respondents could not afford to feed their children with 3 square meals a day while 79.2% of the respondents could not afford to train their children in school but allow them to go out to fend for themselves as early as age seven (7) which result to out of school children, crime, and violence with 77%. This study concluded that, unemployment of parents has a major implication on the Nigerian child sustainable development making the child prone to child abuse, drug addiction, banditry, out of school children and high involvement in crime and violence. The study recommends that the Government at all levels should create employment and ensure security, parents can develop capacity for self-employment.

Key words: Unemployment, Development, Sustainability, Child, Economy.

Introduction

Unemployment has become one of the greatest challenges faced by the Sub-saharan African economies which has maintained a rising trend over the years. Unemployment is defined as the proportion of those in the labor forces who are actively looking for work but cannot find work. The total number of people classified as unemployed, which means people who do nothing at all in Nigeria increased from 17.6million to 20.9 million (National Bureau of Statistics, 2018). This figure continues to rise as there are increasing consequences of unemployment across Nigeria. Akeju and Olanipekun (2015) emphasized that unemployment

problem in Nigeria comes in different dimensions. Underemployment cases arise when people receive income that cannot sustain or maintain the basic needs in terms of food, shelter, and clothing.

Sustainable development occurs when the needs of the present are met without compromising the ability of future generation to meet their own needs,(Kuhlman and Farrington, 2010, Chang, Lehmann, Winter and Finkbeier,2018). Child sustainable development refers to development which supports children to meet their needs now and in the future., however, these prospects

can be in disarray if parents cannot cater for the needs of children, which can result to undesirable consequences.

Crime, violence, inadequate living conditions, banditry, out of school children, poor nutrition, are challenges faced by societies because of unemployment, (Isiaka and Okaphor, 2018). defined crime as a legal wrong for which the offender is punished at the instance of the state. Violence on the other hand bears detrimental impact on a child's development. Violence affects the development of a child's brain (UNICEF, 2017). Childhood exposure to violence and crime can lead to serious consequences for the health and wellbeing of those exposed both during childhood and throughout adulthood (Shonkoff, Boyce and McEwen, 2009.) Children exposed to violence and crime are more likely to abuse drugs and alcohol; suffer from depression, anxiety, and posttraumatic stress disorder; fail or have difficulties in school; and become delinquent and engage in criminal behavior, (Fang, Brown, Florence and Mercy, 2012). Olaniyi (2019) emphasized that education is widely regarded as the route to economic prosperity, the means to combat poverty, the key to scientific and technological advancement, literacy, and the foundation of social equity. The population of out of school children in Nigeria has risen from 10.5 million in 2010 to 13.2 million in 2015 (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2017). Over 45 percent out of school children in West Africa are Nigerians, which has ranked Nigeria as having the highest number of out of school children in the world. Many reasons have been advanced for out of school children in Nigeria. These include economic reasons, early or forceful marriage of girls, insecurity, parental, social and peer group influence (Olaniyi, 2019).

Wayas, Selvadurai and Awang (2019) states that insecurity problem in Nigeria is a major factor contributing to unemployment. The tension between Fulani herdsmen and farming communities has escalated in recent times to include unending attacks, kidnapping and killings by the nomads. Individuals are constrained with the fear of

been killed by Boko Haram, bandits, kidnappers, and herdsmen who operate with sophisticated arms such as AK-47 rifles attacking at midnight killing indiscriminately, burning down houses and looting properties. Many individuals quit their jobs in areas with no security, relocating to safer environment thus, may become unemployed. Evans and Kelikume (2019) disclosed that Boko Haram bandits, one of the world's deadliest terrorist organizations has consumed thousands of lives over the past years displacing millions of persons from their livelihoods leading to high rate of unemployment and displacement of people from their abode. There are 2.3 million Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) and many more in refugees' camps fleeing from Boko Haram leaving their jobs and farmlands, (Evans and Kelikume, 2019).

Nwankwo and Ifejiolor (2014) disclosed that in recent times, unemployment which is caused by lack of job placement opportunities, has joined the list of the social evils experienced in Nigeria today. The Agricultural sector has been the leading provider of employment in Nigeria especially for more than 60% of Nigerian population in the early 60s and 70s (Nwankwo and Ifejiolor, 2014), however, the attention has been redirected to the oil sector where employment capacity is very low to job seekers who have no place in the oil industry. Furthermore, there is no special provision of credit/loan facilities for rural or agricultural endeavors, (Ibikunle, Orefuwa and Mafo, 2019).

The process of strengthening access to credit through rural institutions is a challenge than capacity development alone. The poor-economic environment in the rural settings has continued to pose serious threats to employment generation in Nigeria mostly, therefore leading to rural-urban migration. If again, parents are unemployed and incapacitated financially, this has a double-edged prong of effects on children. Usworth (2007) argued that parental unemployment status exhibit behavior of bullying, truancy, and school exclusion in children. Unemployed parents face challenges of

taking up children's educational responsibilities, this often, result into out of school children. Arbeit (2013) reported that children of unemployed parents encounter delays in behavioral growth, cognitive development, educational ambition, self-concept, self-esteem, classroom behavior and educational progress. All these interfere with children sustainable development.

Problem of the Statement

With the growth of unemployment, the economic inequality between the poor and rich keep growing given rise to more social tensions which in turn affect the entire sphere of the community. Parental unemployment could have adverse effect on children's health and wellbeing and even quality education which are the major keys in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Parental unemployment could be detrimental to the wellbeing of children which is likely to lead children into crime and violence. The worst-case scenario is that of people looking for jobs opportunities but cannot find any either in the public or private sector. People are also willing to set up some form of business but are constrained by the prevailing poor macro-economic environment. All these contribute to the problem of high level of unemployment and adverse poverty among parents in Nigeria and these can influence the wellbeing of the child.

Objectives of the study

The study was guided by the following objectives.

1. To examine the employment status of parents in Samaru, Basawa and Dogarawa wards of Sabon-Gari Local Government Area.
2. To identify the causes of unemployment among parents in Samaru, Basawa and Dogarawawards of Sabon-Gari Local Government Area.
3. To examine the impact of parents' unemployment on the children in Samaru, Basawa and Dogarawa wards of Sabon-Gari Local Government Area.

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Descriptive survey research design is that type of design that seeks to obtain data from subjects of their preferences, opinions, attitudes, and behaviors. The design was deemed appropriate for this study because the researcher elicited data from the respondents on influence of unemployment on the Nigeria child.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised of four hundred (400) parents in three selected wards from Sabon-Gari Local Government (Samaru, Basawa and Dogarawa). The population was drawn from the list of landlords/house owners' association in these areas.

Sampling and Sampling Technique

A sample of twenty (20) percent of the total population of the study area were selected for the study which was in four hundred (400) parents from three (3) wards in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area. Multistage and purposive sampling techniques were used. The various stages in the sampling were at stage one Sabon-Geri local Government Area was stratified into 11 wards: stage two was the random selection of three wards from the 11 wards; stage three involved the purposive selection of eighty (80) parents.

Method of Data Collection

A self-structured questionnaire titled; "Parents Employment and Sustainable Development Questionnaire (PESDQ)" was used as the instrument for data collection with a reliability coefficient of 0.85. The instrument comprised of twenty-six (29) items. The instrument was validated by three Senior lecturers at National Agricultural Extension Research and Liaison Services, Ahmadu Bello University.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics of percentages and frequency counts.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study are presented on Tables 1-3.

Table 1 shows that 73 respondents representing (91.6%) were not employed, 60 (58.7%) are fully employed but not satisfied with their jobs, 55 (68.7%) of the

respondents agreed looking for work or trying to establish own businesses. Other results on parents' employment status showed parents who are fully at home and not bothered to seek for work, parents who work in both public and private sector and parents who operate their own business.

Table 1: Percentage Responses on Parents' Employment Status in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State. N=80

S/N	Item	F	(%)
1	Not employed	73	91.6
2	Fully employed and satisfied with the job	10	26.3
3	Employed but not satisfied with the job	60	58.7
4	Looking for work or trying to establish own business	55	68.7
5	Fully at home and not bothered about looking for work	20	25.0
6	Would you prefer to be working or you are unemployed by choice	46	56.6
7	Employed in a public sector/government	25	68.7
8	Employed in a private sector	35	44.0
9	Self-employed and operating own business	15	32.6

Table 2 shows causes of unemployment among parents in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State. The respondents' response on this reviewed that negligence of agricultural sector, especially people not engaging in farming of all types (90%), insecurity/ other crisis (81.1%) and poor quality of graduates (85%), rural-urban

migration of the farming workforce, insufficient work spaces for the number of graduates, bottle necks for start businesses, funding, limited access to loans, poor enabling environment and lack of employable skills are the causes of parents unemployment.

Table 2: Percentage Responses on the Causes of Unemployment in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State N=80

S/N	Item	A	(%)	D	(%)
1	Negligence of Agriculture (people are not engaged in farming)	70	90.0	10	10.0
2	Insecurity crisis	75	81.2	5	18.8
3	Poor quality of graduates	67	85.0	13	15.0
4	Rural-urban migration, especially of the farming workforce	65	81.2	15	18.8
5	Insufficient workspaces for the number of graduates	60	75.0	20	25.0
6	Government bottlenecks in startup businesses	44	55.0	36	45
7	Misappropriation of funds meant for development projects	64	79.2	16	20.8
8	Limited access to credit/loans for small enterprises in the rural areas	60	75.0	20	25.0
9	Poor enabling environment	70	87.4	10	12.6
10	Lack of employable skills	20	24.9	60	75.1

Table 3 shows results on the influence of parents' unemployment on child sustainable development. Majority of the respondents representing 74 (76.3%) agreed to not affording a 3 square meal, 73 (79.2%) respondents agreed

on out of school children and a total of 62 (77%) agreed to crime and violence as the effect of parental unemployment on children sustainable development.

Table 3: Percentage Responses on Influence of Parents' Unemployment on Children Sustainable Development (N=80)

S/N	Item	A	(%)	D	(%)
1	Cannot afford 3 square meals	74	76.3	6	23.7
2	Contributes to out of school children	73	79.2	7	20.8
3	Crime and violence	62	77.0	18	23.0
4	Drug addiction	68	75.0	12	25.0
5	Low self esteem	53	66.2	27	33.8
6	Child abuse	60	75.0	20	25.0
7	Increase level of poverty	70	76.0	10	24.0
8	Decline in quality life	68	71.6	12	28.4
9	Unhealthy home environment	67	74.9	13	25.1
10	Increase in banditry activities and social vices	15	18.7	65	81.3

Discussion on Findings

From the findings on table 1, the result revealed that greater percentage of the respondents were not employed (91.6%) while (58.7%) were employed but not satisfied with their jobs and (26.3%) fully employed and satisfied with their jobs. This result agreed with the findings of National Bureau of Statistics (2018) that the total number of people classified as unemployed, which means they did nothing at all in Nigeria increased from 17.6million in Q4 17 to 20.9 million Q3 2018. Individual unemployment can be because of numerous setbacks which include, loss of previous job or rise in the number of persons searching for jobs, which could occur because of people previously outside the labor force decided to join the labor force. Underemployed occurs in person working less. It could also be a situation where people engaged in activity that underutilizes their skills and educational qualification. Rural farmers who work only seasonal on their farms only during planting and harvest period and do nothing in between can also be classified as unemployment. National Bureau of Statistics (2020) stated that employed persons are persons engaged in the production of goods and services, thereby contributing to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDPs) in a rightful way. Akeju and Olanipekun (2015) lamented

that the problem of unemployment in Nigeria comes in different dimensions. Underemployment in Nigeria arises when people work and receive little incomes that cannot sustain or support their basic needs like food, shelter, and clothing. The worst-case scenarios are those looking for employment and are legible but cannot find any job for themselves.

The findings on table 2 shows result on the causes of unemployment among parents in the study area. Respondents agreed to negligence of agricultural sector and other natural resources due to over dependence on crude oil (90%) as the major cause of unemployment. Agriculture has been recognized as one of the leading sustainable employments in Nigeria (Nwankwo and Ifejiolor, 2014). Attention has been completely drawn to the oil sector neglecting the agricultural sector and other available natural resources where the employment capacity is very low to those seeking for jobs with no place in the oil industry. Table 2 findings further reviewed insecurity (81.1%) as a cause of unemployment. This finding agreed with the study of Wayas, Selvadurai and

Awang (2019) which stated that insecurity has become a major factor contributing to unemployment in Nigeria. The tension between Fulani herdsmen, bandits, kidnapers, and 'Boko Haram' has escalated in recent times to unending attacks, kidnapping, killings, burning of houses and farm produce, looting properties, and rapping women and children. Communities are no longer safe for individuals and families. People are being constrained with the fear of being killed by those who now operate with sophisticated arms attacking and killing indiscriminately. The damage on lives and properties, brutality and impunity caused by insecurity has forced many to flee leaving their farmlands, jobs and businesses. Low standard of education was further agreed to be a cause of unemployment by the respondents with (85%). Ibikunle, Orefuwa and Mafo (2019) revealed that the proliferation of institutions of higher education and the over-emphasis on certification is responsible for unemployment in Nigeria with graduates leaving school without any skills for work.

Table 3 considered not affording to have a 3 square meal (76.3%), out of school children (79.2%) and crime and violence (77%) as the effects of parental unemployment on the Nigerian child. Arbeit (2013) noted that children of unemployed parents face hardship, encounter delay in growth because of poor nutrition, school challenges, with low self-esteem. Fang, Brown, Florence, and Mercy (2012) reported that child maltreatment, peer victimization and exposure to family and community violence have all been shown to be connected to developmental issues. Children exposed to violence and crime are more likely to abuse drugs and alcohol; suffer from depression, anxiety, and posttraumatic stress disorder; fail or have difficulties in school.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study looked at the employment status of parents in some selected wards from Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State and the implication of parents' unemployment on the child sustainable development. Therefore, the study concludes that unemployment status of parents has

adverse influence on the child sustainable development. Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. Agriculture is the largest employer of labor in Nigeria. Hence, attention should be given to the agriculture by government and families. The agricultural value chain can become the hub for creating more jobs. This would not just reduce the high rate of unemployment but also feed the nation as well
2. Providing Security is the responsibility of the state, therefore for agriculture to receive boost for subsistence and economic purposes, security of lives and property must be guaranteed.
3. Parents should develop capacity building for self-employment, cottage businesses can develop to ensure sustainable development.

Reference

- Akeju, F. K. & Olanipekun, B. D. (2015). Unemployment and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of African and Asian studies* 11. 92-98.
- Arbeit, A. C. (2013). *Is Timing Everything? parental unemployment and children educational Attainment*. 2013-12.
- Chang, Y., Lehmann, A., Winter, L. & Finkbeier, M. (2018). The sustainable child development index (SCDI) for countries. *Sustainability* 10 (5) 1563.
- Evans, O. & Kelikume, I. (2019). The impact of poverty, unemployment, inequality, corruption and poor governance on Nigeria Delta militancy, Boko Haram terrorism and Fulani herdsmen attacks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences* 8 (2) 58-80.
- Fang, X., Brown, D.S., Florence, C.S. & Mercy, J.A. (2012). The economic burden of child maltreatment in the United States and implications for prevention. *Child Abuse & Neglect* 36 (2):156-165.
- Ibikunle, G., Orefuwa, E. R. & Mafo, A. B. (2019). Analysis of the causes and effects of unemployment in Nigeria

- towards a solution for Graduate idleness and poverty alleviation. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)* 24 (2) 36-44.
- Isiaka, A. A. & Okaphor, F. E. (2018). Concept of Crime in the Administration of Penal Justice in Nigeria: An Appraisal *NAUJILJ* 9 (1):246-251.
- Kuhlman, T. & Farrington, J. (2010). *What is sustainability?* 2: 3436-3448.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2018). *Labour Force Statistics Volume-1: unemployment and underemployment Report (Q4 2017- Q3 2018)*.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2020). *Labour Force Statistics, unemployment, and underemployment Report - Q2 2020*.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF). (2017). *Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey 2016-17, Survey Findings Report*. Abuja, Nigeria: National Bureau of Statistics and United Nations Children's Fund.
- Nwankwo, C. A. & Ifejiolor, A. P. (2019). Impact of unemployment on Nigeria economic development. A study of selected Local Government Area in Anambra State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management* 6 (33) 103-112.
- Olaniyi, O. A. (2019). Comparative Studies of Out of School Children in Three African Countries. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3477930> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3477930>.
- Shonkoff, J.P., Boyce, W.T. & McEwen, B.S. (2009). Neuroscience, molecular biology, and the childhood roots of health disparities: Building a new framework for health promotion and disease prevention. *Journal of the American Medical Association* 301(21):2252-2259.
- UNICEF (2017). *A Familiar Face: Violence in the lives of children and adolescents*. New York: UNICEF, p. 24.
- Usworth, L. (2007). *The impact of parental employment and unemployment on children and young people*. An unpublished PhD thesis submitted to the University of Nottingham.
- Wayas, G. G., Selvadurai, S. & Awang, A. H. (2019). An examination of the causes of unemployment among youths in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering* 8 (12s2) 567-573.